

Compressed Sensing Recovery using Computational Memory

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Abstract— Computational memory (CM) is a promising non-von Neumann approach where certain computational tasks are performed within resistive memory units by exploiting their physical attributes. We propose a new method for fast and robust compressed sensing (CS) recovery of sparse signals using CM. For a signal of size N , this method achieves a potential $O(N)$ -fold complexity reduction compared with a standard software approach. Large-scale experimental demonstrations using more than 256k phase-change memory (PCM) devices are presented along with an in-depth device analysis and array-level considerations.

I. INTRODUCTION

A computational memory (CM) unit when incorporated into a computing system (Fig. 1) is attractive for performing computationally expensive tasks of a high-level algorithm in an energy-efficient manner. For instance, crossbar arrays of resistive memory (memristive) devices can be used to store a matrix and perform analog matrix-vector multiplications at constant $O(1)$ time complexity without intermediate movements of data [1]. This capability is well-suited for solving complex optimization problems, such as compressed sensing (CS) recovery. CS is used in various applications, such as MRI, facial recognition, holography, or in mobile-phone camera sensors, where it allows a significant reduction of the signal acquisition energy by capturing only few measurements (e.g. 10%) instead of the whole signal [2]. However, CS recovery algorithms are usually complex, and conventional implementations are confronted with limited scalability owing to the large number of operations involved and high memory requirements. CM offers the potential to significantly reduce the memory and computing resources needed to solve the problem as well as its computational complexity, which could enable CS applicability to big data problems, in particular IoT devices and systems.

II. COMPRESSED SENSING

The basic idea of CS is to acquire a signal at sub-Nyquist sampling rates and recover that signal accurately (Fig. 2) [3]. The CS reconstruction problem is to determine the signal x_0 from the measurements y when sampled as

$$y = Ax_0 + w, \quad (1)$$

where A is a $M \times N$ measurement matrix with $M \ll N$, and w represents the measurement noise. CS asserts that if the signal x_0 is sparse in some transform domain ($x_0 = \Psi\xi$, where ξ is sparse), it can, under certain conditions, be recovered from y .

An appealing alternative to standard convex optimization methods to solve (1) is approximate message passing (AMP), because of its low computational complexity [4]. The AMP algorithm to recover x_0 given y and A is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} x^{t+1} &= \eta_t(A^*z^t + x^t) \\ z^t &= y - Ax^t + \frac{N}{M}z^{t-1}\langle\eta'_{t-1}(A^*z^{t-1} + x^{t-1})\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\langle\cdot\rangle$ denotes the mean, and $\eta_t(\cdot)$ is a (nonlinear) function; x^t is the current estimate of x_0 at iteration t , z^t is the current residual, A^* is the transpose of A , and $x^0 = 0$.

III. REALIZATION USING COMPUTATIONAL MEMORY

The key idea of realizing CS using CM is to encode A as conductance values of memristive devices organized in a crossbar array. The compressed measurements (1) are acquired by applying x_0 as voltages to the crossbar rows, and y is obtained as the resulting output current at columns (Fig. 3). The matrix-vector multiplications $q^t = Ax^t$ and $u^t = A^*z^t$ required for AMP recovery in (2) can be efficiently implemented using the same crossbar array (Fig. 3). In this way, the complexity of (2) is potentially reduced from $O(MN)$ to $O(N)$. Negative matrix elements can be coded on separate devices together with a subtraction circuit, and negative vector elements can be applied as negative voltages. The additional vector operations in (2) are implemented in a dedicated digital processing unit (Fig. 4).

We implemented CS with AMP recovery using a prototype multi-level PCM chip fabricated in the 90-nm technology node (Fig. 5) [5]. Analog storage of conductance values is achieved by varying the amorphous/crystalline fractions (Fig. 6). The element-by-element multiplications of the matrix-vector product were realized in the PCM chip, and the remaining operations were implemented in software. The elements of A were mapped to conductance values between 0 and 50 μS and programmed on 4 PCM devices averaged per element using iterative programming. Fig. 7 shows the conductance distributions for 5 representative levels. We mapped the vector entries to voltage values between 0 and 0.3 V using a nonlinear mapping $f(V)$ to account for the slight nonlinearity of the current-voltage (I - V) characteristics of PCM devices (Fig. 8). To prevent errors in the multiplication results due to conductance drift of the PCM devices, we developed a drift calibration procedure which consists in periodically reading the summed conductance of S devices in the array to account for a global conductance shift during an experiment (Fig. 9). This simple procedure is easily implemented in a crossbar array, and estimates the conductance variations directly from the devices without any assumptions on how the conductance changes. The accuracy of the matrix-vector computation with our PCM chip is comparable to that of a fixed-point implementation where the matrix and vector elements are quantized to 4 bits (Fig. 10).

IV. EXPERIMENTAL DEMONSTRATIONS

A. Compressed sensing of sparse random signals

We implemented CS with AMP recovery on the PCM chip for a random signal x_0 of size $N = 256$ with 64 i.i.d. Gaussian non-zero entries. We programmed a measurement matrix A in the PCM chip with i.i.d. Gaussian entries normalized such that the norm of its columns is approximately 1 [4]. The measurements were obtained by computing $y = Ax_0$ with the

PCM chip, and subsequently reconstructed with AMP using the chip to compute the matrix-vector operations Ax^t and A^*z^t . A soft-threshold function was used as $\eta_t(\cdot)$ with a sequence of thresholds $\tau_t = \|z^t\|/\sqrt{M}$ [4,6].

The evolution of the normalized mean square error (NMSE) $\|x^t - x_0\|^2/\|x_0\|^2$ between the original and reconstructed signals is shown in Fig. 11 for sampling rates $M/N = 1$ (no compression) and $M/N = 0.75$. The convergence rate of AMP is unaffected by the approximate multiplications done in the PCM chip, but, in contrast to a full double-precision floating-point implementation, the NMSE floors after ~ 10 iterations. The magnitude of the NMSE floor obtained with the PCM chip is comparable to that obtained in an implementation where the multiplications in Ax^t and A^*z^t are done in 4x4-bits fixed-point. Still, the PCM implementation recovers the general shape and sparsity pattern of the original signal well (Fig. 12).

B. Compressive imaging with image denoising

Here x_0 represents the pixel intensities of an image. The goal is to acquire this image with $M \ll N$ measurements and reconstruct it accurately. We used the methodology described in [6] to implement compressive imaging with AMP, which uses an image denoiser $D_{\tau_t}(\cdot)$ instead of $\eta_t(\cdot)$ in (2) with estimate τ_t of the standard deviation of the noise. We used the 128x128 ‘‘house’’ image as signal x_0 and a 50% sampling rate. We divided the image into 16x16 pixel blocks, compressed each block using a 128x256 Gaussian measurement matrix encoded in the PCM chip, and reconstructed the image. Fig. 13 shows the evolution of the NMSE for wavelet thresholding and BM3D denoisers. We found that using a better denoiser (e.g. BM3D) improves the reconstruction accuracy by mitigating the errors from the PCM chip. A PSNR > 27 dB was obtained for both denoisers with the PCM implementation (Table 1).

V. DEVICE AND ARRAY-LEVEL CONSIDERATIONS

We thoroughly evaluated the effect of device imperfections on the final reconstruction NMSE obtained in Section IV.A through system-level simulations, assuming $M/N = 0.75$ and 30 AMP iterations. A first source of error is conductance variations due to programming errors or conductance noise. Programming errors distort the matrix, but do not prevent convergence of AMP as long as the errors are randomly distributed across the array, because the Gaussian nature of A is preserved (Fig. 14). Conductance noise, in contrast, is detrimental because it introduces incorrigible random errors in the AMP algorithm at every matrix-vector operation, which will lead to NMSE floor (Fig. 14). Conductance noise in PCM arises from both the $1/f$ noise of the amorphous phase-change material and drift variability [5], and we believe that it is the dominant source of error in our experiments. Another error source is I - V nonlinearity, which prevents having a true Ohm’s law for analog multiplications if voltage amplitude is used as input variable. In PCM, $I = \alpha_1 \sinh(\alpha_2 V)$ is an accurate model of low-voltage I - V [7]. Using this model to simulate the device response to input voltage, we found that the NMSE is not affected for α_2 values up to 5 (moderate nonlinearity), but it degrades for stronger nonlinearities (Fig. 15). I - V nonlinearity can be overcome by using a nonlinear mapping between input vector and voltage as done in our experiments, or using pulse

duration instead of amplitude as input variable. Besides device imperfections, device failures can also occur in a memristive array. In PCM, failure mechanisms include elemental segregation (stuck-SET) and void formation (stuck-RESET) [8]. Stuck-RESET failures (randomly distributed, up to 20%) can be tolerated and do not prevent convergence of AMP (Fig. 16). However, even a small amount of stuck-SET failures (< 1%) leads to poor performance of AMP because the normalization of the matrix is no longer fulfilled (the norm of the columns becomes >1 because of the high-conductive devices). A simple way to correct for this is to renormalize the matrix-vector multiplications accordingly, which can be done with a procedure analogous to what we used for drift calibration (Fig. 9). In this way, AMP converges even with up to 20% random stuck-SET failures (Fig. 16). This amazing resilience to device failures is because the CS matrix elements simply need to be random, but their exact magnitude does not matter. Finally, the achievable reconstruction NMSE assuming ideal devices will be ultimately limited by the resolution of the DACs/ADCs used at the input/output of the crossbar array. To obtain a final NMSE of $\sim 10^{-4}$ (same as floating point), a resolution of at least 8 bits is necessary (Fig. 17).

In (2), matrix-vector multiplications are the most expensive operations, so we compared the memristive crossbar analog multiplier with a 4-bit FPGA multiplier design. The 4-bit matrix elements are stored in the FPGA block-RAM and 32 dot-product units operate in parallel to compute a 256x256 matrix-vector product in 1.2 μ s. A 256x256 PCM-based crossbar engine operating at 1- μ s cycle time is expected to consume 50 times less dynamic power than the FPGA design (Table 2). The power benefits arise because only read operations are performed in the memristive crossbar for multiplications, which consume little energy (1 - 100 fJ per device for our 90-nm PCM) and can be performed with unlimited endurance, as no reprogramming of the devices is needed.

VI. CONCLUSION

We proposed a new method for CS recovery where the measurement matrix is stored in a memristive crossbar array. The same array can be used to perform the matrix computations associated with both the compression and recovery tasks in a non-von Neumann manner. This method can achieve a $O(N)$ -fold recovery complexity reduction compared with a software implementation, without requiring more iterations to converge. Experimental demonstrations show the array-level robustness of the scheme for > 256k PCM devices, and a detailed analysis demonstrates its resilience to device imperfections and failures.

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Fig. 1. Architecture of CM accelerator attached to conventional computing system. In CM, computational tasks are performed within the memory units without intermediate data movements.

Matrix A programmed only once in crossbar. Same crossbar used for measurements and reconstruction.

Fig. 3. $N \times M$ memristive crossbar acquires the CS measurements y and realizes the matrix-vector computations $q^t = Ax^t$ and $u^t = A \cdot z^t$ of AMP recovery algorithm.

Fig. 5. (a) Layout, (b) picture and (c) specifications of PCM chip with integrated read/write circuitry used for experiments.

Fig. 6. Analog storage achieved on PCM chip with single-shot programming from RESET.

Fig. 8. Current of the 5,000 PCM cells programmed in Fig. 7 read at voltages between 0 V and 0.3V. (a) Plotting vs. $G_T \cdot V$ (G_T : target conductance) results in poor overlap of the levels due to I - V nonlinearity. (b) Using nonlinear map $f(V) = V + 5V^3$ results in better overlap.

Fig. 2. In CS, a large input signal is acquired with few compressed measurements. Reconstructing the signal from the measurements is complex because an underdetermined linear system must be solved (fewer equations than unknowns). Unlike transform coding (JPEG, MPEG compression), CS performs sampling and compression simultaneously (only a few measurements are acquired instead of the whole signal).

Fig. 4. AMP recovery using memristive arrays: All matrix-vector computations are realized in the memristive arrays; the other vector operations in a dedicated digital processing unit.

Fig. 7. Iterative programming of 5 conductance levels (vertical lines in (b)) on 5,000 cells of PCM chip. (a) Iterations to convergence. (b) Conductance distributions read 50 μ s after programming. (c) Conductance distributions over time. Filled areas are $\pm\sigma$ bounds. Drift exponent ν computed from $G(t) = G(t_0)(t/t_0)^{-\nu}$.

Fig. 9. Calibration procedure to prevent errors in multiplication results from our PCM chip due to conductance drift. Procedure was performed on $S = 10,000$ devices at every 5 matrix-vector multiplications.

Fig. 10. $y = Ax_0$ computed with PCM chip. A is 256×256 Gaussian matrix coded in PCM chip, x_0 is a 256-long Gaussian vector applied as voltages, y_i is the i -th element of y . Result is comparable to doing 4x4-bit multiplications.

Fig. 11. Experimental reconstruction NMSE as a function of the AMP iterations for CS with soft-thresholding for a signal size $N = 256$. Filled areas: $\pm\sigma$ bounds over 16 different combinations of random A and x_0 .

Fig. 12. Experimentally reconstructed signal with PCM chip for one of the experiments of Fig. 11 (0.75 sampling rate).

Fig. 13. Experimental reconstruction of 128×128 “house” image signal (50% sampling rate) for wavelet thresholding and BM3D denoisers used in AMP (algorithm of [6]).

Fig. 14. Effect of conductance variations on reconstruction NMSE. Programming errors do not prevent AMP convergence, but noise determines NMSE floor.

Fig. 15. Effect of I - V nonlinearity on reconstruction NMSE. Voltage range used is $0 - 0.3$ V.

Fig. 16. Effect of device failures on reconstruction NMSE. Stuck-SET failures can be circumvented by renormalizing the CS matrix. Fluctuations in final NMSE occur because the matrix is highly distorted due to the failed devices. However, AMP still converges, and lower NMSE can be obtained by doing more iterations.

Fig. 17. Effect of DAC/ADC resolution at input/output of crossbar on reconstruction NMSE. Resolution gives lower limit of minimum NMSE that can be reached.

Table 1. PSNR (in dB) of 128×128 “house” image reconstructions.

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{\|\hat{x} - x_0\|^2 / N} \right),$$

where \hat{x} is the estimate of x_0 .

	PCM chip	Fixed-point	Floating-point
Wavelet threshold	27.15	27.39	32.50
BM3D	34.58	32.27	45.06

Table 2. Comparison of 256×256 FPGA 4-bit matrix-vector multiplier and 256×256 PCM-based crossbar CM.

	FPGA	Computational memory (estimate)
Design	Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale (20 nm), 32 dot-product units with 4-bit inputs, 250 MHz clock	256×256 crossbar + 2 8-bit ADCs @ 125 MS/s, 256^2 1T1R PCM cells, 90nm node
Time	1.18 μ s	1.02 μ s
Dynamic power	800 mW	16.1 mW
Energy	944 nJ	16.4 nJ
Area	9629 LUT (1.46%), 5713 FF (0.43%), 32 BRAM (1.48%)	0.0433 mm ²